

ISic0623

Fragmentary Latin inscription

Language

Latin

Type

honorific (?)

Material

marble

Object

fragment

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Found in excavations during March 1952 in the presumed area of the ancient city, the area of trenches 6 and 8 (not precisely located) in the Piano between Pizzo Cisterna and the Castello

Coordinates

38.05720, 15.10404

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, (near) Tripi, Current location unknown

Physical Description

Fragment of a marble slab, broken on all sides

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Remains of two lines of Latin letters

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

thinly incised regular letters with minimal serifs

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. [---]nius[---]

2. [---]Ivir[---]

Apparatus

Text based upon drawing in NSA 1954

Translation**Commentary**

This is the only Latin inscription from the vicinity of Tripi (ancient Abacaenum/ Abakainon) and the apparent reference to a duumvir is commonly understood to indicate that the town had the status of a (Latin) municipium by some time in

the first (or second) century AD. However, it is also often suggested that the settlement fell within the territory of the colonia of Tyndaris in the imperial period.

Digital identifiers:

TM 175831

EDR 074064

EDCS 13700406

Bibliography

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Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. *Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535.* Warminster. At 43 n.96

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. Notizie degli scavi di antichità. At 49-50 fig.4

Bacci, G.M., Coppolino, P. 2009. *La Necropoli di Abakainon: primi dati.* Messina. At 13 fig.2

Sofia, G. 2015. *Abakainon. Nella dimora di Ade. La necropoli in contrada Cardusa a Tripi. Terme Vigliatore (ME).* At 109 fig.114

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Scan of NSA 1954 p.49 fig.4